

Creating a Scientific Workflow to Manage Old Italian Texts

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The management and analysis of extensive collections (corpora) of texts is a complex task, encompassing both technological and scientific considerations. Researchers involved in textual studies (including, but not limited to, philologists, palaeographers and codicologists) do not merely extract information from texts; they also examine visual elements—such as layout and *mise-en-page*—and physical characteristics of written materials such as printed books and manuscripts. Their analysis includes text structure, material used, word layout on the page and any annotations or notes. The development of efficient scientific workflows to handle these diverse aspects is a significant challenge in the field of digital humanities. The following article describes a scientific workflow supporting the management of Old Italian texts, offering innovative integration of semantic technologies and philological methods to enhance scholarly digital editions.

Keywords: text corpora management, text corpora analysis, Old Italian texts, digital humanities, scientific workflows, scholarly digital editions

Astratto

La gestione e l'analisi di vaste collezioni di testi (corpora) costituisce un compito complesso, che comprende considerazioni sia tecnologiche che scientifiche. I ricercatori che si occupano di studi testuali (tra cui, ma non solo: filologi, paleografi e codicologi) non si limitano a estrarre informazioni dai testi, ma esaminano anche le caratteristiche visive (cioè l'impaginazione e la *mise-en-page*) e materiali (cioè la fisicità) dei materiali di scrittura (cioè libri stampati e manoscritti), tra cui la struttura del testo, il materiale utilizzato, la disposizione delle parole sulla pagina ed eventuali annotazioni o note. Lo sviluppo di flussi di lavoro scientifici efficienti per gestire questi diversi aspetti è una sfida significativa nel campo delle digital humanities. L'articolo che segue descrive un flusso di lavoro scientifico a supporto della gestione di testi in italiano antico, offrendo un'integrazione innovativa di tecnologie semantiche e metodi filologici per migliorare le edizioni scientifiche digitali.

Parole chiave: gestione di corpora testuali, analisi di corpora testuali, testi in italiano antico, digital humanities, workflow scientifici, edizioni digitali accademiche

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Conflict of Interest

The authors do not have any conflict of interest to declare

1 INTRODUCTION

This article presents and discusses a scientific workflow supporting the management of textual resources written in Old Italian. Drawing on the experience and activities carried out by DARIAH-IT,¹ this paper describes the methodological considerations and technological solutions devised to address the intricate range of linguistic, textual and philological issues posed by documents dating from the Middle Ages. Since 2022, DARIAH-IT has participated in the H2IOSC (Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud) project,² whose primary goal is to facilitate data-driven research by enabling users to design and run complex scientific workflows, combining different resources (i.e. digital data and/or services) to produce meaningful and replicable research outputs. By linking together different resources, users can automate complex analytical tasks and extract meaningful insights from data. Within the H2IOSC project, DARIAH-IT also develops a number of scientific pilots: custom Virtual Research Environments supported by digital data, tools and services tailored to support specific kinds of disciplinary research, which serve as usable representations of the above approach. To develop the pilots (and hence the workflows), presented as platforms or hubs integrating domain-specific services, workflows and interfaces, DARIAH-IT undertook a set of preparatory activities. These included mapping and evaluating existing resources (tools, datasets and services) relevant to the target scientific communities (e.g. philologists). To build solid use cases, research data management is essential for ensuring the long-term accessibility, reproducibility and impact of the researcher's scholarly work. Effective data management practices not only improve the quality of research; they strengthen the credibility and transparency of the findings.

These efforts are closely aligned with the objectives of the DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group,³ as it, too, seeks to promote best practices, facilitate data sharing and help build sustainable digital infrastructures for the arts and humanities. The good practices shared in this context (through discussion, documents and reference libraries⁴) offered reflection points that could be applied to the work carried out by DARIAH-IT. The preparatory work described in this introduction resulted in a workflow to manage Old Italian textual data in an integrated environment.

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1. DARIAH-IT is the Italian node of DARIAH ERIC (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, European Research Infrastructure Consortium), an ESFRI Landmark for the Social and Cultural Innovation sector. DARIAH-IT's headquarters are located at the research institute Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR).
 2. H2IOSC is a federated cluster comprising the Italian branches of four European research infrastructures (RIs) active in the Social Sciences and Humanities ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) domain. These are DARIAH, CLARIN, E-RIHS and OPERAS. The H2IOSC project is funded by Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), which aims to facilitate collaboration among researchers working in different disciplines within the social sciences and humanities. Further details can be found on the project's website: <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>.
 3. The DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group (<https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups/research-data-management/>) is a collaborative initiative that addresses the challenge of sharing and preserving research data in the arts and humanities. It brings together researchers, cultural heritage professionals and data management experts to develop best practices, support open scholarly infrastructure and facilitate access to data.
 4. For more information on the references shared by the DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group, see https://www.zotero.org/groups/2427138/data_management_best_practices_in_the_humanities.

The main steps of the workflow are: data acquisition from stakeholders; data modelling using ontologies; semantic parsing; transformation into semantic data; storage and documentation of code; and querying of data through semantic technologies (e.g. SPARQL endpoints). Each of these steps is designed to address the complexities inherent in Old Italian textual data. It is clear, therefore, that a tailored workflow is required to deal with the specific linguistic and textual characteristics of Old Italian.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 CONTEXT

Modern Italian has often been compared to Old Italian (Ascoli 1882; Castellani 1980) in the perspective of a substantial continuity from Latin to the language spoken today. A fundamental element in this vision of linguistics studies is the Florentine vulgar tongue used by Dante and his contemporaries in the XIII–XVI centuries, making the language spoken in Tuscany the de facto standard for the common Italian language. However, while the thesis of a linguistic continuity of the language was almost uncontested until the last century, more recently, philological and linguistic traditions have given rise to different approaches to the origin and evolution of Italian. These studies either advocate the separation of old and modern Italian (Salvi and Renzi 2010), or provide different perspectives to approach the problem. Interest has also been rekindled in the different regional variants of Italian. Even in contemporary Italy, there are significant differences between regional variants and dialects, reflecting the complex history of a country that was only officially unified in 1861.⁵

Given the complexity of the panorama just outlined,⁶ and in order to have common chronological references, this article uses the term “Old Italian” for all the available historical documentation from the first document that can be called Italian (albeit doubtfully), namely the early-ninth-century Veronese Riddle (*Indovinello Veronese*⁷), until the end of the fourteenth century (a symbolic year, which is sometimes freely exceeded, is 1375, the year of Boccaccio’s death). This clarification is necessary because the period may differ slightly from what is stated in the scientific literature.⁸

While scholarly discussions around the linguistic and historical development of Old Italian are extensive, this paper explicitly focuses on the digital methodologies and technological tools developed to effectively manage and exploit historical textual data through digital workflows. DARIAH-IT supports researchers working on manuscripts containing Old Italian texts by applying different technologies to the complex task of managing resources, including storing, mapping, cleaning, modelling and visualising data.

5. A comprehensive account of how the Italian language developed historically, including its structural shifts and socio-political dimensions, can be found in Lepschy and Lepschy (2006) and Marazzini (2009).

6. To delve deeper into the panorama of romance languages, see Tomasin (2019).

7. *Indovinello Veronese*. Circa eighth—ninth century. Manuscript marginalia, Biblioteca Capitolare di Verona, codex LXXXIX. See also Schiaparelli (1924).

8. See, for example, the *Collins English Dictionary*: <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/old-italian>.

The difference between old and modern Italian editions lies not only in linguistic form but also in editorial practice. Old Italian editions present texts in a language which, although normalised for readability, is not modernised: spelling is standardised, abbreviations are expanded and punctuation is clarified, yet the original lexicon, syntax and verb forms are preserved (e.g. *ond'io, core, vedeasi*). These editions rely on a rich critical apparatus based on multiple, often conflicting, manuscript witnesses, aiming to reconstruct a version close to the lost original. In contrast, modern Italian editions usually derive from autographs or typed drafts authored by the writers themselves, and the language already adheres to contemporary standards. The critical apparatus here serves to document the creative process, highlighting revisions, stylistic variations and editorial interventions rather than textual recovery.

To understand the linguistic divergence between old and modern Italian, consider this example from Petrarch's *Canzoniere*, edited according to philological standards, which reads: "*Voi ch'ascoltate in rime sparse il suono / di quei sospiri ond'io nutriva 'l core*" (Petrarca 2004). This version maintains the original lexicon (*core* for "cuore" *ond'io* for "con cui io") and syntax. In contrast, a version in modern Italian might read "*Voi che ascoltate, in versi sparsi, il suono / di quei sospiri con cui nuttivo il cuore*",⁹ which adapts both vocabulary and structure to modern Italian norms. While the latter is more accessible to today's readers, it alters the poetic and linguistic fabric of the source. It is important, therefore, to highlight critical editorial choices in distinguishing between faithful transcription and modern reinterpretation.

2.2 USE CASE

The development of a workflow for Old Italian texts was first implemented within the framework of the RESTORE project.¹⁰ Co-funded by the Regional Council of Tuscany and coordinated by the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR), RESTORE focused on the medieval period and the historical figure of Francesco di Marco Datini.¹¹ The objective was to develop a digital platform fostering the FAIRification¹² of the digital assets (both new and legacy) gathered by several GLAMs¹³ and research organisations. This in turn would enable the ingestion, conversion, mapping and integration of heterogeneous datasets to overcome the high degree of fragmentation and lack of interoperability of the digital resources provided by

9. This modernised rendering is adapted for illustrative purposes and does not reflect a critical edition.

10. The RESTORE (smaRt accESs TO digital heRitage and mEmory) project, co-funded by Regione Toscana (Regional Council of Tuscany), was coordinated by the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR), partnering with GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) institutions and offices in the city of Prato. The project consortium included Prato's key cultural and memory institutions: the Prato State Archive (*Archivio di Stato di Prato*), the Palazzo Pretorio Museum (*Museo di Palazzo Pretorio*), the *Soprintendenza Archivistica e Bibliografica della Toscana*, and *Space SpA* (SME) as a commercial technology provider. For a comprehensive introduction to the RESTORE project see Degl'Innocenti et al. (2023).

11. Francesco di Marco Datini was a merchant from Prato, Italy, who established a successful commercial network across Europe during the fourteenth century. For more on Datini, see Hayez and Toccafondi (2012); Melis (1959, 1966).

12. The FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) Principles are guidelines designed to enhance data reuse by ensuring it is properly managed and shared in ways that facilitate both human and machine access (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

13. Galleries, libraries, archives and museums.

the partners. The case study described in this paper is the result of DARIAH-IT's involvement in H2IOSC and RESTORE.

The resources used to build the RESTORE case study include:

- archival descriptions of resources preserved by the Prato State Archive, composed of XML-EAD files and authority records compliant with the EAC-CPF Schema;¹⁴
- artwork records from Palazzo Pretorio Museum based on the ICCD (Italian Central Institute for Cataloguing and Documentation) standards for works of art, exported in XML format;¹⁵
- lemmatised corpus of Datini Letters from the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano, with the text encoded in a custom XML markup that maps lexical items, anthroponyms and toponyms;¹⁶
- images (JPG format) of documents from the state archive and the art collection of the museum.¹⁷

The raw resources were first stored in CKAN¹⁸ in their original format. To ensure the reliability and consistency of the datasets, particular attention was paid to data quality, considering the structural, syntactic and semantic levels. The heterogeneous nature of the original sources, produced over decades by different institutions and often lacking common standards, meant that a thorough process of data assessment, cleaning, normalisation and validation was necessary. During the ingestion phase, each dataset was subjected to structural checks to verify compliance with its respective schema (in the use case we are presenting: EAD, EAC-CPF, ICCD, TEI), ensuring integrity and syntactic alignment. Semantic quality was checked through compliance with controlled vocabularies, authority files and standardised mappings used in the project, which allowed for the disambiguation of entities (e.g. people, places, institutions) and reconciliation of variant forms. Ambiguities and inconsistencies, particularly common in legacy data, were resolved in collaboration with domain experts (archivists, philologists and curators), who played an active role in refining mappings and validating content. The use of persistent identifiers (Uniform Resource Identifiers, URI) further supported consistency across the datasets, enabling accurate linking and traceability. Documentation of

14. The Encoded Archival Description (EAD) is an Extensible Markup Language (XML) standard for encoding archival finding aids, facilitating the description of archival records and enhancing their discoverability. The EAC-CPF Schema is a standard for encoding contextual information about individuals, organisations and families associated with archival materials using XML. The standard is maintained by the Society of American Archivists in partnership with Berlin State Library.

15. The Italian Central Institute for Cataloguing and Documentation (Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione, ICCD) is an Italian governmental institute belonging to the Ministry of Culture, responsible for defining procedures, standards and tools for cataloguing and documenting cultural heritage.

16. The Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) is a text-centric community that develops and maintains guidelines for encoding digital texts, providing a set of XML tags to represent textual metadata, structure and other features of interest, primarily in the humanities.

17. All of the aforementioned resources were provided by the partner institutions of the RESTORE project. Specifically, the Prato State Archive furnished the archival descriptions, Palazzo Pretorio Museum contributed the artwork records, and the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano provided the lemmatised corpus of letters. The images were linked both to the Prato State Archive and Palazzo Pretorio Museum.

18. The Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN) is an open-source, web-based system for storing, cataloguing and distributing data.

the whole process was also carried out using tools like JupyterLab¹⁹ and Gogs²⁰ to ensure transparency, reproducibility and long-term sustainability of the integrated data environment.

The workflow is designed with the aim of creating a Linked Open Data (LOD) system that integrates the existing resources.²¹ Since it is also necessary to consider how the user can activate (i.e. execute) the steps described in the workflow, its design further implied defining:

- the information available to the user (and therefore acquirable by the machine);
- the format and presentation of the proposed solutions based on the user's request;
- the monitoring process for the operations performed (policies, data management plans or similar tools).

To address the needs of different possible target user groups (e.g. archivists, lexicographers and citizen scientists), the system also required tailored search and visualisation options. To avoid a one-size-fits-all approach, DARIAH-IT developed distinct data visualisation blocks (or contexts, i.e. custom views on data) to be hooked to the workflow for each user group.

In the RESTORE use case, we applied our workflow to the partially lemmatised corpus of Old Italian letters by Francesco di Marco Datini, provided by the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano, extracting both document metadata (sender, recipient, date, place, shelfmark, etc.) and embedded linguistic features to construct a comprehensive knowledge graph. The descriptive metadata was aligned with shared vocabularies and authority files, ensuring terminological consistency across archives, research institutes and museums. Traditional text-processing methods often falter when faced with the linguistic particularities of these documents, which include abbreviations, variant spellings and inconsistently referenced entities; all of these aspects can significantly impede digital research. To address these issues, in the parsing phase, custom algorithms—explicitly designed to handle the mapped peculiarities of Old Italian texts—resolve abbreviations and standardise orthographic variants. In the subsequent transformation phase, semantic alignment and CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM)-based ontology mapping unify divergent entity references and encode the original content into structured semantic triples. In the user interface, the integrated graph is presented through three coordinated panels: (1) alternating-views metadata: juxtaposing each source's records; (2) transcription viewer: offering diplomatic or critical editions (where available) with version-toggle controls; (3) lemma table: listing every annotated form, each marked with part of speech, hyperlemma and, where available, a hyperlink to its entry in the *Tesoro della Lingua Italiana* (TLIO) vocabulary.

19. JupyterLab is a web-based interactive development environment for Jupyter Notebooks, code and data; a Jupyter Notebook is an open-source browser application that allows users to create and share documents containing live code, visualisations and narrative text (such as explanations and descriptions).

20. Gogs is a self-hosted Git service written in Go, aiming to provide a simple, stable and extensible solution for hosting Git repositories.

21. On the benefits of an LOD knowledge ecology, see Brown and Simpson (2015).

This example illustrates the potential of the workflow for managing historical documents. In the following section, we offer a detailed explanation of its constituent components.

3 BEST PRACTICES

To increase efficiency, transparency, rapid dissemination of resources and facilitate reuse, it is good practice to store data according to open access policies and guidelines. The H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management state that “data should be as open as possible, as closed as necessary” (European Commission 2016, 4).²² These best practices are also comprehensively described and documented by the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) Principles, which provide simple guidelines to track and access data, integrate it with other data and reuse it in new research. In Europe, the Horizon 2020 framework programme and its Open Research Data Pilot have promoted activities related to the data collected, generated and used in research projects, strongly recommending the implementation of FAIR Principles. This is known as data management: the creation, organisation, structuring, storage and sharing of data. Resources can be made available through a wide variety of channels, each offering different platforms and user interfaces with distinct qualities and characteristics.

There are currently several publishing systems that start with direct data exchange,²³ while in the past they relied on traditional self-hosted web server downloads, generic or specialised data repositories, non-profit platform infrastructures or providers of commercial applications. The panorama of tools available for data management is broad²⁴ and there is already a large set of established solutions for publishing data, but the support of the FAIR Principles is still a hot topic.²⁵ These platforms currently provide the means to upload and publish datasets with a general, disciplinary or institutional purpose. They also meet the specific needs of multiple stakeholders in different usage scenarios.

Given the context described, the next section will outline the steps of the proposed workflow, illustrating how the technological and methodological choices directly address the identified requirements.

22. See also the “Open Access and Data Management” section of the H2020 Online Manual: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm.

23. An example is Edition Visualization Technology (EVT). EVT is an open-source software framework developed for the visualisation of critical and diplomatic digital editions encoded in TEI-XML. Designed to support scholarly editing, EVT allows for the visualisation of complex textual features, such as variants, annotations and manuscript structures, within an intuitive web interface. It has been widely adopted in digital philology projects due to its flexibility, user-friendliness and adherence to standards in the digital humanities. For more information, see <http://evt.labcd.unipi.it/>.

24. The European Commission recognises the significance of effective data management and its relevance across diverse academic disciplines. The panorama is complex and needs to be analysed to achieve the objective of a data-driven society: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en.

25. The discussion around FAIR data has generated several models for FAIRness evaluation. In 2020, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) published its FAIR Data Maturity Model (Research Data Alliance 2020). The EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) FAIR-IMPACT project has also proposed several solutions for evaluating FAIRness: <https://www.fair-impact.eu/fair-assessment-tools>. These few examples testify that there is still space for further discussion on the topic of evaluating the FAIR Principles.

4 WORKFLOW

4.1 STRUCTURE

The DARIAH-IT team defined a domain workflow for Old Italian text. A domain workflow may be composed of application workflows addressing specific tasks. Our workflow consists of seven main steps, each of which is an application workflow that performs a specific task needing to be completed:

- **Data acquisition from data providers:** the first step is acquiring data from the stakeholders. The data is therefore stored in a container that ensures swift management of the materials. This approach, first validated in RESTORE, has been specifically adapted for Old Italian texts by incorporating specialised XML annotation formats that manage the linguistic and lexical intricacies characteristic of these historical sources.
Reference technologies: CKAN, a well-known open-source platform for the publication of open data collections, aimed at organisations that publish data (national and local governments, companies and institutions) and wish to make it open and accessible to all.
- **Parsing of data on the Entity–Relationship model:** to foster interoperability and semantic coherence, data must be processed to ensure the conceptual alignment of information expressed through different semantic schemes and/or structures, by combining elements belonging to one dataset with those of another if both express the same concept. This can be achieved by processing data to clean, normalise and compare pieces of information.
Reference technologies: custom Python scripts developed by DARIAH-IT.
- **Data modelling:** the goal of data modelling is to formalise knowledge (i.e. translate it into a formal language), to minimise its ambiguity (typical of natural language)²⁶ and make it machine-readable so that inferences can be made about it using algorithms. Data becomes structured according to the rules of the reference ontology,²⁷ which will form the basis for transforming the datasets into semantic triples. Building on methods established within the RESTORE project, the modelling strategy adopted here explicitly addresses the semantic complexity of Old Italian textual data, integrating the CIDOC CRM ontology to manage philological nuances, palaeographic annotations and lexical ambiguity (Coradeschi et al. 2021).
Reference technologies: CIDOC CRM, a flexible ontology for structuring concepts and information in cultural heritage and museum documentation.
- **Data transformation:** the data is transformed into semantic triples to exploit the information identified during the mapping process.
Reference technologies: custom Python scripts developed by DARIAH-IT, the 3M tool.²⁸

26. On the theoretical foundations and implications of using ontologies to make sense of metadata, see Canning et al. (2022).

27. On scientific workflows and their underlying structures across disciplines, see Liu (2017), who identifies shared data “moves” in data-intensive research and the potential role of libraries in supporting brittle points in data trajectories.

28. The Mapping Memory Manager (3M) is a system designed to manage mapping files for XML file schema and underpins the 3M Editor: a suite of applications that helps experts complete the mapping definition process.

- **Code storage and documentation:** all steps in the workflow are to be documented and the code is to be accessible according to open science principles.²⁹
Reference technologies: Jupyter Notebook.
- **Importing data to the triplestore:** the semantic triples are imported in a storage for triples. The triples are atomic semantic statements following the SPO (Subject–Predicate–Object) structure enriched with persistent URIs for entities and properties. The resulting RDF data was loaded into a Virtuoso triplestore, enabling semantic querying and integration via SPARQL endpoints. The data can therefore be interrogated through semantic queries.
Reference technologies: OpenLink Virtuoso, a multi-model data server offering a platform-independent solution for data management, access and integration. Virtuoso is thus a hybrid database that combines the functionality of a traditional Relational Database Management System (RDBMS), Database Management System (DBMS), virtual database, RDF, XML, web application server and file server into a single system. The Virtuoso triplestore also enables a SPARQL endpoint.
- **Semantic data browsing:** through semantic queries, the data can now be interrogated to exploit information and generate new knowledge.
Reference technologies: there are two main ways to use the SPARQL endpoint of the DARIAH-IT triplestore to harness the data and perform semantic searches: Facet Browser and LodLive (visual conceptual browser). Facet Browser is an interface tool integrated with SPARQL endpoints in Virtuoso databases, allowing users to explore and filter linked data by facets—categories of metadata such as date, author or location. In digital humanities, this tool is particularly useful for navigating complex datasets by narrowing down results based on specific attributes, making it easier for researchers to discover relationships and patterns within large cultural datasets. LodLive is a visualisation tool for exploring Linked Open Data through SPARQL endpoints, such as those hosted on Virtuoso. It provides an interactive, graph-based view of RDF data, showing connections between entities in real time. In digital humanities, LodLive enhances research by visually mapping relationships between entities, such as historical figures, places and events, helping scholars contextualise and analyse data within a broader network of cultural information.

29. Open science is a movement aimed at making scientific research and its dissemination accessible to all levels of society. Its principles include open access to publications, open data, open-source software, open methodology, open peer review and open educational resources. See <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>.

WORKFLOW		DATA		
COMPLEX	UNITARY	TECH/PLATFORM	INPUT	OUTPUT
DATA MANAGEMENT TOOL SUITE (RAISE-BE)	DATA CLEANING AND PROCESSING		XML-based standards: EAD, EAC, ICCD, TEI	CSV files
	DATA MAPPING AND MODELLING		CSV files	Semantic triples: TTL Ontology (CIDOC, FOAF) & Vocabulary (GETTY, REPETTI, ICONCLASS)
SEMANTIC DATA INGESTION TOOL SUITE	DATA IMPORT		Semantic triples: TTL	UPLOAD TO VIRTUOSO
DATA VISUALISATION TOOL SUITE (RAISE-FE)	QUERY MANAGER	JAVASCRIPT	QUERY SPARQL	JSON
	DATA BROWSING		GUI plain text	Aggregated data visualisation / data clusters (JS, HTML, CSS)
RAISE ATLANTE MODULE	DATA VISUALISATION		JSON	MAPS & TIMELINE (leaflet.js, timeline.js)
DATA VISUALISATION SPECIALISED TOOLS	IMAGE AND TEXT VIEW	EVT	XML TEI standard	Digital Scholarly Edition Visualization (Online)
	STORYTELLING		Plain text, images	Virtual Exhibition Online
	LOD VIEW		Endpoint SPARQL	Graph representation
DATA STORAGE	WORKFLOW CONFIGURATION AND DOCUMENTATION		PARSER, DATA etc.	Workflow, code, and data in a web-based interactive development environment
	STORAGE OF DEVELOPED COMPONENTS		PARSER, DATA etc.	Components in a GIT repository
	RAW DATA INGESTION		XML-based standards: EAD, EAC, ICCD, TEI	Visualisation and storage of original datasets

Figure 1: workflow description

Figure 1 summarises the workflow steps to ensure that textual data—regardless of its origin, format or institutional context—can be integrated into a unified, semantically expressive knowledge base that meets the FAIR Principles and supports cross-domain interoperability.

4.2 MODELLING

The suite of tools developed to manage the RESTORE use case applied to the described workflow has been deposited in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) Open Marketplace as “RAISE—Restore dATA Integration Suite.”³⁰ The SSH Open Marketplace serves as a central hub where the SSH research community can deposit, discover and share research workflows. As a discovery platform, the SSH Open Marketplace brings together a wide range of curated digital resources (including tools, services, datasets, publications and training materials) and contextualises them to support every stage of the research data life cycle (Barbot et al. 2023b). Within this environment, workflows play a key role as structured, step-by-step representations of research methodologies, linking each phase of the process with relevant resources (Barbot et al. 2023a). Moreover, the workflows developed within

30. See RAISE on the SSH Open Marketplace at <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/plyy0d>. For more information, see Degl’Innocenti et al. (2021).

DARIAH-IT can certainly benefit from comparison with other experiences described in the SSH Open Marketplace. In fact, other research projects deal with the same issues in data management.

The value of the DARIAH-IT workflow lies in its ability to handle the semantic integration of highly heterogeneous cultural heritage data, including archival descriptions, museum catalogues and lemmatised textual corpora. Unlike more generalised workflows, it is specifically designed to address the challenges posed by fragmented legacy resources, varied metadata standards and domain-specific semantic ambiguities. Its complex architecture, established by the organisation in connected blocks, ensures both technical robustness and scholarly relevance. Moreover, the workflow incorporates mechanisms for differentiated data visualisation and user interaction, recognising diverse digital literacy levels and research needs. By combining rigorous methodological principles with domain expertise, DARIAH-IT enables a level of precision, contextualisation and cross-resource interoperability that significantly enhances the study of Old Italian within the mapped context.³¹

Underlying this complex workflow is the delicate role of ontologies, which by definition are formal representations of knowledge shared by a community. An ontology defines entities and properties to describe a knowledge domain in a formal organisation. In the described workflow, ontologies are used to model data in order to:

- describe the structure and hierarchy of the formal models for encoding data (e.g. archival data like EAD), information about the producing entities (e.g. EAC), and the ministerial records used to describe cultural heritage (ICCD);
- describe the legacy of the resources, especially the context of provenance;
- allow integration with other ontologies and conceptual models related to more specific domains (e.g. Ric-O³²).

As a Conceptual Reference Model, the DARIAH-IT team chose the CIDOC CRM for its consolidated use in the social sciences, humanities and cultural heritage domain.³³ CIDOC CRM is a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage. It achieves this by providing definitions and a formal

31. In the SSH Open Marketplace, several workflows are identified as particularly relevant to the themes addressed by the RESTORE project and serve as useful comparative references. The workflow [LODification of Bibliographical Data: Zotero to Wikibase Migration with ZotWb](#) provides insight into lightweight strategies for transforming bibliographic metadata into Linked Open Data, particularly through reconciliation and semantic enrichment. [A Workflow to Publish Collections as Data: The Case of Cultural Heritage Data Spaces](#) offers a clear framework for ensuring ethical openness, transparency and computational reuse of cultural heritage resources, emphasising practical publishing practices. The [Bibliographical Data Science: From Catalogues to Research Data](#) workflow demonstrates robust methods for harmonising and validating structured metadata, especially in multilingual and transnational contexts, underscoring the importance of authority reconciliation. Finally, [Making Data Interoperable for the Semantic Web](#) outlines a technically comprehensive process for aligning domain-specific datasets with ontological models, emphasising vocabulary alignment and triplestore publication. While these workflows address specific facets of data transformation and publication, the RESTORE workflow integrates many of their principles into a unified, domain-specific pipeline tailored to the complexities of historical and linguistic resources.

32. Records in Contexts-Ontology (Ric-O) is an OWL ontology for describing archival record resources and their contextual entities; see <https://www.ica.org/resource/records-in-contexts-ontology/>.

33. Suffice it to say that the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) reference model is also based on the CIDOC CRM ontology: “SSHOCro is modelled as an extension of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM)” (Bekiari et al. 2022).

structure to describe implicit and explicit concepts and relationships used in cultural heritage documentation and of general interest for querying and exploring such data. Significantly, such models, also known as formal ontologies, enable data from heterogeneous sources to be integrated.³⁴

5 TOWARDS A WORKFLOW FOR DIGITAL EDITIONS

The workflow described in this article has been designed to address the peculiarities associated with Old Italian texts, which present methodological and technological challenges requiring dedicated solutions. Compared to modern Italian, managing Old Italian texts is complex due to their linguistic variability, non-standardised orthography, palaeographic abbreviations and the instability of manuscript and early printed textual transmission. The phases of data acquisition, parsing, modelling, RDF transformation and semantic querying included in this workflow specifically reflect the peculiarities of medieval documents: the adoption of CIDOC CRM, specialised lemmatisation, textual collation and representation through *stemma codicum*, directly addresses philological requirements absent from workflows designed for contemporary texts, which will be fully implemented in the Digital Philology Hub, a DARIAH pilot in the H2IOSC project.

To illustrate an extension of the workflow's capabilities, consider a corpus transmitted through multiple medieval manuscripts, some of which have already been digitised in early pioneering editions. The materials to be edited digitally may include high-resolution manuscript images, diplomatic or critical transcriptions, critical apparatus, variants and annotations.

Researchers working with such richly layered data face considerable challenges. They must integrate transcriptions, lemmatisation, textual variants, glossaries and metadata, and link these to external digital resources (for example, manuscript catalogues, lexical databases and other scholarly repositories). Conventional tools typically fall short in supporting these integrated scholarly workflows, focusing on specific tasks instead of the whole study process.

If modern Italian texts were involved, many orthographic and linguistic normalisation procedures would be unnecessary, significantly reducing the complexity of parsing and textual annotation tasks. The tools involved should therefore be adjusted or trained to deal with modern Italian. The steps of the applicative workflow may remain the same, but each unitary workflow (i.e. step) composing the whole process would need to be revised to deal with different kinds of texts.

Nevertheless, while designed to address the peculiarities of Old Italian, the modular nature of our workflow enables it to be scaled and adapted efficiently to other textual traditions facing similar challenges. Indeed, the semantic modelling provides a flexible structure that can be readily adjusted or expanded upon, allowing researchers working on texts from different historical periods or linguistic contexts to apply similar approaches to their specific needs.

The workflow described in this paper lays the foundation to overcome these obstacles by enabling the structured integration of heterogeneous textual data into a

34. On the transformation of controlled vocabularies into semantic resources, see Vogeler (2025) for an example applied to the field of sigillography.

unified digital environment. It also paves the way for advanced visualisations, such as mapping the provenance of historical documents geographically and through chronological timelines.

Within the H2IOSC project, this workflow is further enhanced to systematically support tasks including manuscript transcription and lemmatisation, precise textual collation, the creation and interrogation of critical apparatuses and glossaries, and seamless linkage to external scholarly resources.

Specifically, DARIAH-IT is coordinating the development of two pilot initiatives: the aforementioned Digital Philology Hub and the Digital Heritage and Memory Hub. These pilots aim to support the implementation of custom Virtual Research Environments to execute scientific workflows within the H2IOSC federation of research infrastructures. In the context of managing textual resources from medieval sources, a key methodological reference has been Leonardi (2021), whose work outlines the fundamental steps of philological analysis. These steps were critical for addressing the specific complexities inherent in processing and interpreting early Italian textual materials. By explicitly addressing specific data needs identified through practical collaborations (such as RESTORE and H2IOSC) and clearly integrating advanced technological solutions, the workflow described in this article offers a coherent and replicable methodological model. Future studies will be able to adapt this workflow to other historical linguistic contexts, taking advantage of its proven ability to effectively handle textual, linguistic and semantic complexities. Indeed, the structured workflow developed here, rooted in the experiences of RESTORE and further refined within the H2IOSC pilot projects, provides a robust and replicable model for academic digital editions of ancient Italian texts, thus significantly advancing the methodological practices of digital philology.

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